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Citizen participation in local energy communities: a meta and weight analysis

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ABSTRACT

Given their strong potential to mitigate environmental problems and contribute to the decarbonization of energy systems, researchers and practitioners are demonstrating increasing interest in local energy communities. Accordingly, the current study presents a meta and weight analysis that combines the quantitative results of previous research on the topic of citizen participation in these communities, revealing the main tendencies, theories, and constructs evident in the field. Through an analysis of 24 articles, the results identify the theory of planned behavior as the leading ground theory, together with important dimensions such as trust, personal characteristics, return on investment, and pro-environmental and altruistic factors. The findings of this work can support future researchers and practitioners in developing strategies to increase the creation of local energy communities.

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Local energy communities; participation; meta-analysis; weight analysis

Introduction

Given the seriousness of current prominent environmental problems, research that investigates ways to mitigate them is expanding. These efforts vary from adopting renewable energies, changing to more sustainable practices, and using more efficient and smart appliances, among other strategies. Regarding the European Union (EU), directives are increasingly identifying interventions to reduce the effects of climate change, especially ways to decarbonize the energy system. One of the strategies currently gaining attention is the implementation of local energy communities. These communities can be defined as neighborhoods that benefit from using renewable energy systems, allowing individuals that legally live in such communities – here defined as citizens – to produce, consume, and sell energy to their neighbors, hence creating a more decentralized and decarbonized energy system (Kühnbach et al. 2022). These communities can greatly benefit from energy independence, both at social and economic levels, since costs are better distributed and tariffs are usually much lower (Azarova et al. 2019). Therefore, the role of citizens in these communities is extremely relevant since they are the main active players, which by itself can be seen as an advantage by placing the citizen at the center of the energy market, but also a challenge,

given the strong participation individuals need to have for the success of their energy community (Malik et al. 2022).

Given its importance, the number of studies on citizen participation in local energy communities has recently grown, and the theme is starting to mature, creating an opportunity and demand to provide a comprehensive and synthesized view of the current progress on this topic. Past research has identified several drivers and barriers to citizen participation. From a more practical perspective, the impact of regulations, lack of equipment (Koirala et al. 2018), and financial incentives (Bauwens 2016) have been investigated. From a more social perspective, factors like social norms and environmental concerns have been explored (Broska 2021). Nevertheless, although some systematic reviews have been developed, these have focused on specific topics related to local energy communities, like government instruments or the definition of local energy communities (Capper et al. 2022; Leonhardt et al. 2022). Therefore, a meta and weight analysis that can identify and quantify the impact of the relevant variables and theories has not yet been established. Accordingly, this study aims to conduct a meta and weight analysis of studies devoted to local energy communities, focusing on citizen participation. These methods allow for the

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synthesizing of the findings of quantitative studies and, therefore, are seen as more robust methods than customary literature reviews (Schmidt and Hunter 2004). Overall, a meta-analysis provides a concise understanding of a subject, uncovering the primary relationships and possible gaps, even when previous research might present contradictory findings (Urbach et al. 2009).

By contrast, the weight analysis will complement the results of the meta-analysis by identifying the most frequently used variables and categorizing them as “best” and “promising” indicators (Jeyaraj et al. 2006). Overall, these two methods provide a combination of results from different works, even when they use different techniques and samples, identifying the most significant relationships and most frequently used variables. This work will, therefore, allow one to identify the current state-of-the-art on citizen participation in local energy communities across different countries, models, and types of local energy communities. Although we recognize that only quantitative articles are evaluated, we cannot only identify but also quantify the impact of the main factors investigated in the literature. By doing so, we are able to provide a more statistically robust overview of the topic, identifying current patterns, trends, and effect sizes that are difficult to identify when reviewing studies individually.

Summarizing, the contribution of this article is two-fold. First, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first meta and weight analysis developed on the topic of local energy communities, therefore contributing to a more synthesized view of prior research on this topic. Furthermore, it will allow stakeholders to identify the main patterns, theories, and variables being used, therefore facilitating theory development and the identification of possible research gaps.

The structure of the article is as follows. The next section describes the research methodology, including the selection process of the studies that we analyzed. We then report the results of the meta and weight analysis, including a descriptive analysis subsection of the selected studies. The following section discusses the main findings and outlines the theoretical and practical implications. We then describe the limitations of our approach, survey possible avenues for future research, and offer a few concluding observations.

Research methodology

Selection of studies

In order to select the studies, we conducted a literature review in November 2022, resorting to the

most common scientific databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Science Direct (Webster and Watson 2002). A set of queries was built using specific keywords related to the topic. First, related to the area of study, we searched the following keywords: “local energy market,” “local energy community,” “local flexibility market,” “smart grid community,” and “renewable energy community.” Second, since we wanted to ensure citizen behavior, the following keywords were added: “participation,” “engagement,” “collaboration,” and “participation intention/willingness.” Finally, to exclude qualitative articles, we used the following keywords: “model,” “survey,” “questionnaire,” “regression,” and “structural equation modeling.” Logical operators AND and OR were also used to develop the queries. The initial search resulted in 2,274 articles.

We then developed a set of criteria to retain only the relevant articles, namely (1) studies published under a peer-review process; (2) studies analyzing the citizen perspective; (3) quantitative studies with correlation values and sample sizes; (4) studies with theoretical models, and thus only including more social, behavioral studies; and (5) independent datasets. In instances where the same dataset was used in more than one study, we only include one article to avoid bias from using the same sample (Wood 2008). Figure 1 describes the selection process. After examining the articles, 24 of them met the criteria, with no duplicates found. Each study’s information was recorded, specifically its source, journal, publication year, independent variables, dependent variables, correlation coefficient of each relationship, method, country, and sample size.

Figure 1. Selection process.

Variables merger and relationships

After collecting all relevant information from the selected studies, we searched for variables with different names but the same meaning. This factor led to a merging process described in the Appendix. Therefore, based on the definitions of the variables, variables with similar meanings were merged into a single name, facilitating computational techniques. For example, variables like *environmental concern*, *environmental attitudes*, and *pro-environmental orientation* were merged into a single name, *environmental concern*, encompassing their similar meanings. After the merging process, we were able to identify 121 relationships. While analyzing these relationships, 93 had the intention to participate in a local energy community as the dependent variable, while 14 had attitude. As explanatory variables, we found attitude, education, environmental concern, subjective norm, and income to be more frequently tested factors. Nevertheless, we investigated other dimensions. A set of community-related variables, namely community motivation, solidarity, and resistance, has been examined (Fischer et al. 2021; Goedkoop et al. 2021). Additionally, prior research has investigated the role of factors such as political identification (Leknoi et al. 2022), house characteristics (Azarova et al. 2019; Krietemeyer et al. 2021), social media (Hackbarth and Løbbe 2020), and emotions (Bamberg et al. 2015; Leknoi et al. 2022). However, only relationships that appeared three or more times can be evaluated in the meta-analysis. This facet ensures a minimum level of consistency and robustness in the findings, reducing any possible biases that may be present in individual studies with fewer occurrences of a particular relationship (Baptista and Oliveira 2016). Therefore, only 20 relationships were used for the

analyses. In these relationships, either intention to participate in local energy communities or attitude was identified as dependent variables.

Results

Descriptive analytics

From the 24 studies, it was possible to identify the country samples. Figure 2 presents the sample size cumulative distribution per country. It is pertinent to note that three datasets were not included in the figure, given that samples were from more than one country. Overall, the countries with the most respondents are Germany and Belgium (48% of the respondents), followed by Thailand, India, China, and the United States (9% of the respondents). The map shows a greater number of respondents in Germany and Belgium, which does not necessarily represent more studies conducted in those countries. Nevertheless, we recognize an increasing number of studies, especially in Germany, given its strong efforts in these communities and sustainability technologies overall. Nonetheless, the applied method is robust to different sample sizes, as the effect sizes are also corrected by sample size. In fact, we have used the random-effects model instead of the fixed-effects model since it considers that the studies may be heterogeneous and effect sizes may vary according to each population.

Regarding the journals and research period, the studies range from 2015 to 2022, of which 54% were published in 2021 and 2022, confirming the sharply increased interest and relevance of studying local forms of energy systems. In terms of journals, the prominence of the journals in the energy field is evident, with *Energy Policy* and *Energy Research & Social Science* containing the most articles (46% of

Figure 2. Sample-size distribution.

the studies). Table 1 summarizes the selected studies per journal and year.

Meta and weight analysis results

As regards the meta-analysis, this approach is considered robust since it allows for summarizing quantitative findings from many articles, analyzing the studied topic from a broader and more consolidated perspective (Bommer et al. 2022). The method provides a pooled estimate of the independent variables on the dependent one. Therefore, the main requirements for conducting a meta-analysis are the effect and sample sizes, which reduce potential conversion biases (Roth et al. 2018). The effect sizes were corrected by sample size, and the random-effects model was used since it considers within and between variance among studies (Borenstein et al. 2010). The analysis was conducted using R packages (version 4.0.2). Table 2 presents the meta-analysis results. We started by evaluating the heterogeneity of the studies using Cochran's Q test and the I2 index. In Cochran's Q, the heterogeneity is proven by the significance level (Higgins and Thompson 2002). The I2 presents heterogeneity ranging from 0% to 100% (Higgins and Thompson 2002). We can see that only two

relationships present low levels of heterogeneity. Most relationships display a high heterogeneity level. We also accessed the failsafe number (FNS), consisting of the number of non-significant or unpublished studies that would be necessary to refute the findings of each relationship tested (Rosenthal 1979). Finally, the effect size was checked for evidence of publication bias using Egger's test (Egger et al. 1997), where we evaluated whether the data distribution was a representative sample rather than asymmetric.

The results show that 15 out of the 20 relationships are statistically significant. The statistically significant variables to intention to participate in local energy communities, ordered by effect size, are social identity ($r=0.373$), attitude ($r=0.319$), return ($r=0.291$), perceived behavioral control ($r=0.281$), environmental concern ($r=0.263$), innovativeness ($r=0.196$), subjective norm ($r=0.190$), altruism ($r=0.177$), education ($r=0.135$), trust ($r=0.119$), house ownership ($r=0.106$), knowledge ($r=0.102$), income ($r=0.071$), rural ($r=0.070$), and household size ($r=0.021$). Finally, environmental concern ($r=0.249$) is also statistically significant to attitude.

Regarding the weight-analysis, this method allows for categorizing the explanatory variables according to their predictive power to the

Table 1. Selected studies by journal and year.

Journal	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Total	Articles
<i>Cities</i>								1	1	(Leknoi et al. 2022)
<i>Ecological Economics</i>			1						1	(Bauwens and Eyre 2017)
<i>Energy</i>								2	2	(Hussain et al. 2022; Nketiah et al. 2022)
<i>Energy Economics</i>							1		1	(Cohen et al. 2021)
<i>Energy for Sustainable Development</i>								1	1	(Tsagkari 2022)
<i>Energy Policy</i>		2		1	1	1	1		6	(Azarova et al. 2019; Bauwens 2016; Bauwens and Devine-Wright 2018; Conradie et al. 2021; Engelken et al. 2016; Hackbarth and Löbbecke 2020)
<i>Energy Research & Social Science</i>		1		1	1		2		5	(Fischer et al. 2021; Kalkbrenner and Roosen 2016; B. Koirala et al. 2018; Krietemeyer et al. 2021; Seidl et al. 2019)
<i>Frontiers in Psychology</i>								1	1	(Goedkoop et al. 2021)
<i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i>					1				1	(Kotilainen et al. 2019)
<i>Journal of Environmental Psychology</i>	1								1	(Bamberg et al. 2015)
<i>Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews</i>							1		1	(Piselli et al. 2021)
<i>Renewable Energy Sustainability</i>								1	1	(Wang et al. 2022)
<i>Sustainability</i>							1		1	(Morgan and Canfield 2021)
<i>Extractive Industries and Society</i>								1	1	(Kumar et al. 2022)
Total	1	3	1	2	3	1	6	7		24

Table 2. Meta and weight analysis results.

Dependent variable	Independent variable	O	N	r	CI (95%)	Q	I ²	FNS	Egger's Intercept (sig)	Weight	Type
Intention to participate	Attitude	12	53369	.319	.200 .429	1984.20	99.4%	12604	.055	.92	BP
	Education	10	39622	.135	.063 .207	394.37	97.7%	1310	.403	.90	BP
	Environmental concern	10	37570	.263	.160 .361	798.58	98.9%	7958	.295	1	BP
	Subjective norm	10	16814	.190	.101 .276	262.74	96.6%	977	.052	.90	BP
	Income	7	30130	.071	.038 .104	29.25	79.5%	236	.499	.86	BP
	Female	7	16056	-.089	-.216 .040	380.74	98.4%	23	.253	.43	
	Community identity	7	7684	.075	-.040 .188	149.60	96%	94	.951	.71	
	Knowledge	7	13297	.102	.021 .183	111.95	94.6%	156	.427	.57	
	Household size	5	24267	.021	-.036 .078	30.36	86.8%	21	.418	.40	
	Trust	4	13360	.119	.058 .179	36.46	91.8%	222	.172	1	PP
	House ownership	4	7688	.106	.022 .188	34.40	91.3%	110	.965	.75	
	Perceived behavioral control	4	2546	.281	.182 .375	18.42	83.7%	300	.511	1	PP
	Return	4	26505	.291	.047 .502	842.46	99.6%	1418	.482	1	PP
	Rural	4	7830	.070	.025 .116	10.22	70.6%	54	.317	.75	
	Age	4	9898	-.005	-.025 .014	.71 ^{ns}	0%	0	.330	.25	
	Altruism	3	5668	.177	.134 .220	3.71 ^{ns}	46%	174	.694	1	PP
	Innovativeness	3	11747	.196	.053 .331	35.41	94.4%	266	.648	1	PP
Social identity	3	8676	.373	.174 .544	179.52	98.9%	1203	.388	1	PP	
Costs	3	6170	.000	-.077 .078	11.21	82.2%	0	.837	.33		
Attitude	Environmental concern	4	1768	.249	.179 .316	5.93 ^{ns}	49.4%	164	.124	1	PP

Notes: (O) number of observations taken from the analysis of the studies; (N) number of accumulated samples of the assessed studies; r=correlation found in the studies correct by sample size; CI (95%)=confidence interval; Q=test of heterogeneity at the individual; I²=scale-free index of heterogeneity; (*) = $p < .01$; ns=not significant; NC=not calculated; Egger's intercept=Asymmetry test.

dependent variable (Jeyaraj et al. 2006). The summarization of the cumulative impact of the independent variables is named *weight*, and together with the meta-analysis, it allows us to identify not only the significance but also the strength of the predictors (Jadil et al. 2021). The weight is calculated by dividing the number of times an independent variable is significant by the number of relationships of that same variable with a specific target one. Thus, when the weight equals one, this means all relationships were significant. By contrast, if the weight is zero, then none of the analyzed relationships was found to be statistically significant. In the weight analysis, it is possible to categorize the predictors into "best predictors" (BP) and "promising predictors" (PP). When a variable is tested five or more times, it is well-utilized; then, if it presents a weight higher or equal to 0.8, it is considered a best predictor. However, if the variable is presented less than five times but has a weight equal to 1, it can still be considered a promising predictor (Jeyaraj et al. 2006). Therefore, from all 20 relationships, five were considered best predictors, and seven were deemed promising predictors. The best predictors for the intention to participate in local energy communities are attitude, education, environmental concern, subjective norm, and income. The promising indicators of intention to participate in local energy communities are trust, perceived behavioral control, return, altruism,

innovativeness, and social identity. Environmental concern is also considered a promising indicator of attitude.

Discussion

Citizen participation in local energy communities has been studied using several theories and variables. Overall, this topic has had growing interest from both researchers and practitioners given the social, economic, and especially pro-environmental benefits it provides, being considered a strong mitigation strategy against climate change and contributing to a fairer and decarbonized energy market. Therefore, from the literature review 20 relationships were examined from 24 articles, allowing us to provide a comprehensive review of the state-of-the-art studies about citizen participation in these communities. The meta and weight analysis identified the most significant predictors of citizen participation, as well as the most frequently used theories and dimensions to explain this phenomenon.

Overall, research on citizen participation in local energy communities has been firmly based on the theory of planned behavior (TPB) (Ajzen 1985). Factors such as perceived behavioral control, subjective norms, and attitude are identified as statistically significant predictors. Figure 3 combines the meta and weight analysis results by presenting the resulting research model based on the best and most

promising predictors that are statistically significant for citizen participation in local energy communities. This summarization is highly relevant as it is possible to find the most used dimensions to explain citizen participation. As shown, works on this topic tend to extend TPB by using other dimensions such as trust, personal characteristics, return on investment, and pro-environmental and altruistic dimensions, as these were found to be statistically significant and frequently studied in previous research. We now provide a deeper explanation of why these dimensions have been so frequently studied in the literature.

Regarding TPB, its statistical significance is not surprising, given this theory's strong use and predictive power to explain adoption and participation behaviors (Yun and Lee 2015). Another commonly identified dimension is trust. This finding suggests that individuals must have a sense of trust to participate in this type of community (Binod Koirala et al. 2018), given that the local energy community can only succeed if all neighbors are committed. In addition, it is possible to discern income, education, and innovativeness as personal characteristics strongly influencing the intention to participate, with income and education being considered as best predictors. This finding suggests that individuals with a higher level of income and education and an openness to innovation are more likely to participate in these interventions. Prior research has suggested that high levels of knowledge and education positively affect

the use of sustainable technologies (Wunderlich et al. 2019).

Another important finding is the statistically significant predictor return on investment. This aspect suggests that one main driver for citizens to participate is the expectation of a financial return in terms of both carbon footprint (Berka et al. 2020) and monetary outcomes (Radtke et al. 2022). This finding suggests that a strong motivation is knowing that, in the long term, it is possible to obtain a return on investment in both effort and money.

Finally, it is salient to notice the presence of the pro-environmental and altruistic dimensions, comprising factors such as environmental concerns, with altruism and social identity considered as best predictors. Overall, these communities include a strong pro-environmental component that cannot be ignored. Therefore, individuals who are more concerned about the environment and have more altruistic characteristics and a sense of belonging to a community, favoring shared benefits to personal ones (Warkentin et al. 2017), are much more willing to participate in local energy communities. This finding reflects the pro-environmental motivation of individuals, which is expected given the solid environmental component of the communities. Moreover, it is worth noting that although these communities present a strong social and shared benefit, only the social identity variable was found significant, suggesting the need for further studies in exploring this social dimension.

Figure 3. Model resulting from the meta-analysis.

Note: Numerical values represent the average β . Continuous arrows represent "best predictors"

Theoretical implications

Regarding implications for theory, the first main contribution is the resulting model that combines the cumulative effects of the explanatory variables on the intention to participate in local energy communities. This model presents a set of dimensions that have been used to explain citizen participation. It shows that TPB has been consistently used and extended with dimensions of trust, personal characteristics, return, and pro-environmental and altruistic ones. Thus, by encompassing these main dimensions, the presented model can be used as a support framework for future research. It is also essential to notice that only one main theory has been used, creating an opportunity for new works to arise, using new approaches more related to the citizen-participation perspective. For example, some researchers have examined the role of financial incentives, government support, and costs (Bauwens 2016; Bauwens and Eyre 2017). From a more social perspective, some studies have investigated the role of dimensions related to empowerment (Leknoi et al. 2022). Therefore, there is still room to analyze the participation in local energy communities from other relevant perspectives that complement previous studies.

Practical implications

Concerning practical implications, it is essential to notice the relevant contribution these findings provide to organizations and policymakers. Overall, we were able to identify the most significant dimensions that motivate individuals to participate in local energy communities. Therefore, the use of that information is valuable for the promotion of strategies that boost the implementation of these communities. For example, creating a sense of trust in the community is extremely important. These interventions heavily rely on collaborative work, so it is crucial for citizens to trust their peers. For many individuals, participating in an initiative like this is seen as a risky investment since it does not depend directly on one citizen and requires a long-term perspective of the investment. Therefore, creating initiatives that strengthen the community's spirit and trust in the community peers is essential.

Another dimension that cannot be underestimated is the personal characteristics of citizens. Highly educated citizens and those with a high income who are willing to try innovations are the target bracket for engaging in these communities. This aspect means that strategies should also focus on educating citizens on energy topics and raising awareness of all the benefits of these initiatives, namely the return

they can bring. By contrast, this result also evinces that high-income individuals might show more propensity to participate in local energy communities. This facet means that government support might be extremely relevant in poorer communities. Finally, one last dimension refers to the pro-environmental and altruistic orientations of the citizens. This suggests that it is still necessary to clearly show all environmental benefits and raise more awareness about environmental problems, for example, in forums or demonstrations.

Limitations and future research

This study is not without limitations. The first limitation is related to the selected articles. Many articles were excluded, given that they were qualitative and did not present the necessary quantitative measures for the methods used. Although we recognize that excluding qualitative articles is a limitation, we also strongly believe that being able to not only identify relevant dimensions but also quantify their impact supports the decision to apply a meta and weight analysis. Second, it is important to note that although citizen participation in local energy communities is receiving increased interest, the number of studies on the topic is still somewhat low, meaning that there are many opportunities to better understand this phenomenon, especially from different perspectives that do not necessarily include well-used theories like TPB. For example, some works have examined the role of financial incentives, government support, and costs (Bauwens 2016; Bauwens and Eyre 2017). From a more social perspective, some works have investigated the role of dimensions related to empowerment (Leknoi et al. 2022). Therefore, there is still room to analyze the participation in local energy communities from other relevant perspectives that complement previous studies. We also encourage researchers to consider citizen participation from a more cultural perspective, understanding possible country differences since pro-environmental behaviors can be strongly connected to national cultures.

Conclusion

Local energy communities are one of the most prevalent and newest strategies referred to by the EU to mitigate climate-change problems. However, these communities strongly rely on citizen participation. Therefore, we applied a meta and weight analysis to 24 articles, resulting in 121 relationships. Only 20 relationships were examined, given that only relationships studied three or more times can be evaluated.

As a result, this work provides a set of the most used and statistically significant predictors of citizen participation in local energy communities, showing that despite the diversity of models and country contexts, the factors that influence participation are broadly the same. The study identifies TPB as a ground theory and some dimensions, such as trust, personal characteristics, return, and pro-environmental and altruistic attributes. Therefore, this work provides a comprehensive view of the state-of-the-art of citizen participation in local energy communities and can be seen as both a foundation for future research and a way to help formulate strategies to foster the implementation of these communities.

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Appendix: Variables codification

Final construct	Variables
Intention to participate in a local energy community	Acceptance of local energy communities, active acceptance, community engagement initiative, intention to participate, intention to participate in local renewable energy community, willingness to participate
Environmental concern	Environmental concern, ecological behavior, environmental attitudes, environmentalist, pro-environmental orientation
Attitude	Attitude, attitude toward renewables
Subjective norm	Subjective norms, social norms, advice from others, family, and friends
Knowledge	Knowledge, know-how, literacy, skill
Education	Education, high education
Income	Income, financial resources
Community identity	Community identity, community affiliation, community identification, identification with the community
Female	Female
Altruism	Altruism, altruistic value
Return	Available rewards, perceived high return, return on investment, financial gain
Household size	House size, household size, number of households
Perceived climate change	Climate change, perceived climate change
Innovativeness	Attitude toward innovation, technological innovativeness
Risk	Perceived high risk, riskiness
Costs	Costs, price of technology
Trust	Trust
Perceived behavioral control	Perceived behavioral control
Age	Age
House ownership	House ownership, owner
Rural	Rural
Social identity	Social identification, social identity
Perceived usefulness	Perceived usefulness, relative advantage
Community resistance	Community resistance
Technical interest	Technical interest
Awareness	Awareness
Government support	Government response, government support
Negative emotions	Negative emotions
Independence	Energy independence
Job creation	Job, job creation
Natural gas	Natural gas
Social curiosity	Social curiosity
Patience	Patience
Elementary or secondary school	Elementary or secondary school
Community solidarity	Community solidarity
Professional training	Professional training
Willingness to change behavior	Willingness to change behavior
Age 35-45	Age 35-45
Liberal	Liberal
Kids	Kids
Male	Male
Protest	Protest
Transparency	Transparency
Age 45-65	Age 45-65
Wind farm	Wind farm
Years in home	Years in home
Challenges	Challenges
Age > 65	Age > 65
Negative reciprocity	Negative reciprocity
Financial incentives	Economic incentives
Ecological political identification	Ecological political identification
Years lived in the community	Years lived in the community
Community administrator	Community administrator
Material	Material
Significance	Significance
Efficacy	Efficacy
Community sustainable energy motivation	Community sustainable energy motivation
Personal norms	Individual norms
Fuel	Fuel
Near plants	Near plants
Retired	Retired
Negative provider experience	Negative provider experience
Infrastructure	Infrastructure
Wood	Wood
Opportunities	Opportunities
Pellet	Pellet
Potential behavior toward energy hub	Potential behavior toward energy hub
Power outage	Power outage
Positive reciprocity	Positive reciprocity
Middle income	Middle income
Conservative political identification	Conservative political identification
Personal characteristics	Personal characteristics
Social political identification	Social political identification
Need for improvement	Need for improvement

(Continued)

Final construct	Variables
Volunteering	Volunteering
Middle age	Middle age
Trialability	Trialability
Low income	Lower income
Urban	Urban
Rented accommodation	Rented accommodation
Experience	Experience
Microgeneration purchase probability	Microgeneration-purchase probability
Positive emotions	Positive emotions
Social media	Social media
Personal sustainable energy motivation	Personal sustainable energy motivation
Part-time job	Part-time job
Absence of connection charges	Absence of connection charges
Student	Student
Apartment	Apartment
Housewife/husband	Housewife/husband
Electricity	Electricity
Participative efficacy	Participative efficacy
Power lines	Power lines
Collective efficacy	Collective efficacy
Heat pump	Heat pump
Image	Image
Gas plant	Gas plant
Political power	Political power